

ELECTRODEPOSITION OF CHROMIUM-MOLYBDENUM ALLOYS

By S. C. SHOME

Alloys of chromium and molybdenum, containing small amounts of the latter metal, have been deposited from solutions prepared by dissolving molybdic acid to the standard chromium plating solution. Bright, semi-bright and dull deposits of the alloys are obtained; the dull metallic plates become bright after polishing. The optimum conditions for the deposition of the alloy have been determined. An alloy containing 1.7% of molybdenum is deposited from a bath containing 400 g./litre CrO_3 , 360 g./litre H_2MoO_4 and 4 g./litre H_2SO_4 at 40° and a current density of 1 amp./sq. in. The deposits formed at higher current densities contain higher percentages of molybdenum and some oxygen.

Industrial chromium plating (Fink, U. S. P. 1,581,158/1926) has been widely used for decorative and protective finishing of metals. Several publications have dealt with the chromium plating but there is very little of information on the subject of electrodeposition of chromium alloys. Fuseya and Sasaki (*Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1931, 59, 445) reported that a chromium-iron alloy containing more than 16% chromium was deposited electrolytically from the sulphate bath using copper cathodes and magnetite anodes. The chromium plating bath, with iron salts added, did not furnish any good deposit of the alloy. Skalozubov and Vlasova (*I Zvest. Novocherkasskogo Ind. Inst. Im. S. Ordzhonikidze*, 1940, 6, 15; cf. *Chem. Abst.*, 1941, 35, 1323) found that the electrodeposition of a protective chromium-nickel coating was possible from a solution containing chromic acid, nickel sulphate and boric acid. Skalozubov and Goncharova (*ibid.*, 1940, 6, 24) described the electrodeposition of iron-chromium-nickel alloys from a solution containing chromic acid, nickel sulphate, ferrous sulphate and boric acid. A corrosion-resistant alloy containing tungsten, chromium and nickel was electrodeposited by Fuchs (B. P. 397,789/1933). Rogers and Burr (*J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1950, 97, 67) obtained electrodeposited chromium-tungsten alloys from a solution of chromic acid, reduced to the trivalent chromium with ammonium citrate, and containing tungstic anhydride.

A good deposit of molybdenum has not been obtained by the electrolysis of its aqueous solution, because molybdenum is one of the metals which are self-polarising (Price and Brown, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1936, 70, 423). When, however, any of the metals such as cobalt, nickel, iron, copper and tungsten was present, molybdenum was easily deposited in the form of an alloy (Myers, 1941, Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, Columbia University, N. Y. C.; Elwee and Holt, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1952, 99, 48; Yntemma, U. S. P. 2,428,404/1947). Considering the possibility of chromium, acting as a carrier of molybdenum in the process of electrodeposition, the present work was undertaken.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Plating Solution.—The solution was prepared by adding a weighed amount of molybdic acid to the chromium plating bath containing 400 g./litre of chromic anhydride. The molybdic acid was dissolved in the chromic acid solution containing the necessary amount of sulphuric acid by efficient stirring with a glass rod.

Electrolysis.—The solution was heated to the required temperature and electrolysed in a 250 c.c. pyrex beaker. Pure copper sheet was used as the cathode and a lead-tin alloy containing 10% tin was used as the anode. The copper specimen, before serving as the cathode, was polished, washed with soap water and then degreased in the vapour of trichloroethylene. The specimen was weighed before and after electrolysis so as to determine the weight of the deposit formed on the cathode. The electrolysis of the solutions was carried out under varied conditions, employing a fresh solution for each experiment.

Analysis of Deposit.—The deposit obtained on the cathode was dissolved in warm 2*N*-HCl and to this solution was added a mixture of 9 c.c. HCl (conc.) and 1 c.c. of HNO₃ (conc.). HNO₃ was added to oxidise the molybdenum to hexavalent state and HCl was used to prevent any slight oxidation of chromium (the trivalent chromium was not oxidised in the presence of sufficient HCl). The solution of chromium and molybdenum was then evaporated almost to dryness in a porcelain basin over a water-bath. The removal of the acid was necessary as otherwise when the solution was treated subsequently with ammonia to precipitate chromium, ammonium salts were formed and chromium salts became easily soluble in excess of ammonia in the presence of ammonium salts. The solution containing chromium and molybdenum salts was then diluted with distilled water and made up to volume in a 50 c.c. volumetric flask. A portion of this stock solution was then treated with a slight excess of ammonia, when chromium was precipitated as hydroxide and molybdenum remained in the solution as molybdate.

The solution was then heated to boiling, filtered and the precipitate was washed thoroughly with hot water. The filtrate and the wash-water were kept aside for molybdenum estimation. The gelatinous chromium hydroxide precipitate, which had absorbed some molybdenum, was again dissolved in warm dilute HCl and the precipitation with ammonium hydroxide was repeated. The two ammoniacal filtrates were then combined and evaporated to a small volume. The molybdenum in the solution was determined by the colorimetric titration method using ammonium thiocyanate and stannous chloride solutions (Grimaldi and Wells, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 315). To run a blank, a pure chromium deposit was treated similarly and the experiment showed the absence of molybdenum in the deposit.

The chromium hydroxide precipitate was dissolved in HCl (dil.), made alkaline with NaOH and oxidised to chromate by adding H₂O₂ solution. The chromate solution was then heated to boiling to decompose the excess H₂O₂, cooled, acidified with HCl and titrated iodimetrically.

The results of the experiments carried out under various conditions are recorded in Tables I to IV.

TABLE I

Effect of concentration of molybdic acid.

CrO₃ in soln. = 40 g./100 c.c. C.D. at cathode = 1 amp./sq. in. Temp. of soln. = 40°
 SO₄/CrO₃ in soln. = 1/100.

H ₂ MoO ₄ taken. (g/100 c.c.)	Voltage of cell.	Time of electrolysis.	Wt. of deposit.	% Current efficiency.	Mo in the deposit.	Cr in the deposit.	Appearance of the deposit.
0	3.1	15 min.	0.0224 g.	13.9	Nil	99.2%	Bright, metallic
2	"	"	0.0220	13.6	"	"	" "
6	3.2	"	0.0190	11.7	"	"	" "
12	"	30	0.0308	9.5	Traces	"	" "
24	3.4	"	0.0128	4.0	0.60%	97.9	" "
30	3.7	45	0.0304	6.3	1.2	97.6	Semi-bright
36	4.0	"	0.0264	5.4	1.7	98.1	Dull, metallic

TABLE II

Effect of temperature.

CrO₃ in soln. = 40 g./100 c.c. C.D. at cathode = 1 amp./sq. in.
 SO₄/CrO₃ in soln. = 1/100.

Temp. of soln.	H ₂ MoO ₄ taken.	Voltage of cell.	Time of electrolysis.	Wt of deposit.	% C.R.	Mo in the deposit.	Cr in the deposit.	Appearance of the deposit.
40°	0 g	3.1	15 min.	0.0224 g.	13.9	...	...	Bright, metallic
"	36	4.0	45	0.0264	5.4	1.7%	98.1%	Dull, "
25°	0	3.3	15	0.0437	27.0	...	...	" "
"	36	4.4	45	0.0426	8.8	1.1	96.2	" "
10°	0	3.5	15	0.0600	37.1	...	...	Burnt
"	36	4.6	45	0.0477	9.8	1.7	95.4	Grey

TABLE III

Effect of current density.

CrO₃ in soln. = 40 g./100 c.c. Temp. of soln. = 40°. SO₄/CrO₃ in soln. = 1/100.

C.D. at cathode. (amp/sq.in)	H ₂ MoO ₄ taken*	Voltage of cell.	Time of electrolysis.	Wt of deposit.	% C.R.	Mo in the deposit.	Cr in the deposit.	Appearance of the deposit.
0.5	0	2.9	30 min.	0.0150 g.	.3	...	...	Bright, metallic
"	36	3.4	90	0.0156	3.2	1.2%	98.0%	" "
1	0	3.1	15	0.0224	13.9	...	...	" "
"	36	4.0	45	0.0264	5.4	1.7	98.1	Dull, "
2	0	3.4	15	0.0319	19.7	...	...	Bright, "
"	36	4.5	45	0.0237	4.9	2.1	93.6	Dull, "
4	0	3.8	15	0.0840	26.0	...	...	Burnt
"	36	6.4	30	0.0100	1.5	5.8	85.6	Grey

* (g/100 c.c.)

TABLE IV

*Effect of concentration of H₂SO₄.*CrO₃ in soln. = 40 g./100 c.c. C.D. at cathode = 1 amp./sq. in. Temp. of soln. = 40°.

SO ₄ /CrO ₃ in soln.	H ₂ MoO ₄ taken.	Voltage of cell.	Time of electrolysis.	Wt. of deposit.	% C.E.	Mo in the deposit.	Cr in the deposit.	Appearance of the deposit.
1/200	0 g.	3.1	15 min.	0.0045 g.	2.8	...	...	Bright, metallic
"	36	4.0	45	...	...	...	...	Brown-black oxide (Cr & Mo present)
1/100	0	3.1	15	0.0224	13.9	...	...	Bright, metallic
"	36	4.0	45	0.0264	5.4	1.7 %	98.1 %	Dull, metallic
1/50	0	3.4	15	0.0165	10.2	...	...	Bright, "
"	36	4.0	45	0.0145	3.0	0.8	97.1	" "
1/25	0	2.4	15	No deposit	...	...	...	...
"	36	3.8	45	Slight	...	...	...	Bright, metallic

DISCUSSION

As the concentration of molybdic acid in the solution is increased, the deposits obtained at the cathode contain higher percentages of the molybdenum metal (Table I). However, the amount of molybdic acid in the chromic acid solution could not be increased to more than 36 g./100 c.c. of the plating solution; the reddish yellow molybdenum chromate was precipitated from the solution with more than this quantity of molybdic acid. The appearance of the electrodeposit changes from bright to dull with the increasing amount of molybdenum in the coating. The dull appearance appears to be due to the fine structure of the deposited crystal and the deposits show metallic lustre when polished. The voltage of the bath is higher with the increase of molybdic acid content of the solution. This might be due to the higher viscosity of the electrolyte or due to the formation of stable compounds of chromium and molybdenum in the solution. The low current efficiency of the alloy deposition seems to be due to the small amount of molybdenum in the deposit, favouring evolution of hydrogen.

The molybdenum content of the electrodeposit did not vary much with the change of the temperature of the plating bath, though a slightly lower value was obtained at 25° (Table II). The appearance of the coatings becomes inferior with the decrease of the temperature of the solution. The current efficiency of the cathodic process increases with the decrease of temperature and this is true whether the electrolyte contains any molybdic acid or not. Electrodeposition at a temperature higher than 40° could not be carried out, since the reddish yellow molybdenum chromate was precipitated as the temperature was raised.

The molybdenum content of the deposits was higher with the increase of the C. D. at the cathode and at C. D. higher than 1 amp./sq. in. The deposit contained a certain percentage of oxide (Table III). A bright alloy of chromium and molybdenum containing 1.2% of molybdenum is formed at a C. D. of 0.5 amp./sq. in., but

in this case both the current efficiency and the throwing power are so low that the cathode surface is not completely covered with the alloy coating even after 90 minutes of electrolysis.

The chromium-molybdenum alloy is best obtained when the SO_4/CrO_3 ratio in the plating solution is 1/100, which is also the optimum value for chromium plating (Table IV). At the lower concentration of sulphuric acid, an oxide coating containing both chromium and molybdenum is formed. A bright coating containing 0.8% of molybdenum was produced when the SO_4/CrO_3 ratio was 1/50, but in this case the cathode was only partly coated owing to the poor throwing power of the solution.

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ELECTROLYTIC ZINC POWDER

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Spongy zinc has been prepared by the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution at room temperature; the sponge crumbles to a fine powder when washed with water and dried. Brass is found to be the suitable cathode and zinc, the anode. Zinc sponge is best obtained from a solution containing 20 to 30% NaOH and 3 to 6% zinc at a cathodic C.D. of 20 to 35 amp./dm². The average current efficiency of zinc deposition is 78%.

In obtaining one pound of zinc powder by the electrolysis of sodium zincate solution using a rotating zinc anode, half immersed in the electrolyte, 0.7 Kw/hr. of electrical energy is required. If an insoluble anode, such as nickel, is employed, 1.5 Kw/hr. of energy is consumed per pound of zinc powder produced.

Zinc powder finds extensive use as a reducing agent in various chemical processes. It is an essential material for the manufacture of sodium hydrosulphite and Rongalite C, which are largely employed in the reduction of dyestuffs in textile industries. Zinc powder is also required for the production of zinc alloys in powder metallurgy.

The methods which can be employed for the preparation of zinc powder are as follows: (i) as a byproduct in the pyrometallurgy of zinc, (ii) by the application of a jet of air to atomize a column of molten zinc, and (iii) by the electrolysis of zinc salt solutions. The powder obtained by method (iii) is chemically more active than that obtained by any of the other methods.